

Moderation effect of Free and Paid Home Delivery option on attitude towards online Shopping: An Empirical Study Using PROCESS

Dr. Sameer Kulkarni, Associate Professor
Amity Business School, Amity University, Mumbai-India

Abstract:

Free home delivery is not only promised by online platforms but equally offered by the physical shops and malls encompassing all types of goods e.g., perishable as well as durable (Gould, 1998; Browne et al., 2001; Hays et al., 2005). During the COVID-19 pandemic the home delivery emerged as a compulsory extension of the main service of sales to avoid the crowd of the individuals at the point of sales (Hobbs, 2020). The add-on of the free home delivery is expected to play a role as a form of value-added service component and expected to influence the buyer in determining their preference for various shopping specifications. Besides, the free-home-delivery is promised by almost all the online platforms, either for special members as a token of appreciation for their loyalty or on special occasions like festival and season sales as an additional element of motivation. Home-delivery (either free or charged) is practiced and offered as a function to ensure the customer's satisfaction (Morganosky & Cude, 2000).

Home delivery is the act performed by the seller by carrying the goods purchased by the buyer to the buyer's doorsteps, without loading any additional charge, just to enhance the feeling of conveyance. The onus of taking the goods from the point of sales to the consumption point, i.e., the buyer's home, is designed to eliminate the perceived barrier acting in the magnitude of the physical distance between the mall or shop and the buyer's residential location. Distance influences the consumer's liberty in deciding the quantity, which otherwise might act as a barrier in case of opting for bulk buying.

This paper attempts to measure the role of home delivery nature as a moderating agent between payment modes and modes of shopping. The test model assigned the specific service offered as 'free-home-delivery', with respect to the two dimensions i.e., consumer socio-demographical characteristics which determines their profile and the type and nature of the goods purchased, by the big scale physical stores. Free-home delivery is expected to perform a much more value-added function than just a last mile logistics activity (Cairns, 1996) equally for the businesses but does the same had been perceived by the individuals?

Key Words:

Home delivery, delivery point, value addition, durable goods, perishable goods, conveyance of delivery, Moderation effect

Introduction:

Delivering the goods at doorstep is no longer a unique phenomenon adopted by the online platforms alone, but now a days it is well adopted by the brick-and-mortar shops also. It has many advantageous features such as saving time and can motivate the buyers to order the goods in large quantities so to avail the quantity discounts and get the benefit of not standing in the billing queues. In the metro cities the eco system revolving around these benefits is considered by the marketers as having enough potential to play as a catalyzer for the busy customers. This paper wants to examine do it is really viewed as a benefit by those who avail it? Or does it act even below their noticeable level?

Consumer preference to buy without visiting the physical setup of any shop just to avoid the limitations of the physical structure and it was a need of the hour during the recent covid pandemic. The obligation to deliver the goods at the buyer's door was an additional responsibility on the shoulder of the retail industry during the pandemic. Afterwards the malls and departmental stores continued to offer the home delivery facility if the habit of getting goods delivered at doorstep may act as a catalyst and it may be explored further to harp in the subsequent non-covid period. It is in extension of the constantly adopting with the style and substance of the consumers. There is no specific study explaining the effectiveness of home delivery as a facility. Specifically home delivery keeps the consumer away or isolated from the vibrant market environment. Physically, visiting the marketplace acts as an act of stress relief due to the indulgence of shopping process. Sometimes consumers prefer to get isolated due to the possibility contamination of infection. One of the impacts observed post covid-19 resulted in the routine shopping activities as the shopping has emerged as a sophisticated activity resulting in the consumers intentionally becoming fickle minded leading in avoiding in the physical shopping activity.

Selection of a typical place for shopping by the consumers has been a specific area of study in the marketing literature. Location preference by the buyers has been addressed as the result of a successful sales strategy. The selection of a typical point of sales has been studied as a part of the physical shop environment, but today's consumer has become habitual to order everything and anything either by looking at the ads in newspapers, i.e., by the offline ads or getting them through web sites as a dynamic source of information, these mode of shopping becomes successful as the shopper are least bothered about the physical location of the shop since the goods are delivered free of charge on the buyer's address.

The present study aims in this regard to measure the influence of home delivery with special reference to the Indian context in a post covid-19-time frame. The study determines the influence of home delivery as a specific facility in the intension of shopping from a specific shop or shopping mall.

Literature Review:

It is proved during the Covid-19 pandemic that the access and availability of the internet has acted as a motivator in the development of preference for buying specifically through online mode. The density and usage of internet for shopping purpose is increasing in India (State of India's Digital Economy,2023). The availability of reliable and faster internet is allowing the potential consumer to conduct the search on the handheld devices rather than by visiting the official web sites. But the physical distance is a real hurdle. Hence some e-commerce sites offer the delivery of the products at no cost to the customers.

The internet users in India has raised by about 40 per cent and the number of smartphone users are bound to become double by the year 2023, it also expects that the core digital sectors are bound to jump by a two-fold and looking to cross USD 355-435 billion by 2025 (Digital India - Technology to Transform a Connection Nation' a report by McKinsey Global Institute, 2019). This paper attempts the impact of this facility of free home delivery as a moderating variable in the preference for buying online.

The facility of home delivery is defined as, "extension of supply chains directly to the end customer" (Kämäräinen et al., 2001; Boyer et al., 2005; Kull et al., 2007; Lim et al., 2018). Many organizations are now started this service executed with some modifications such as, the delivery point can be either the home of the customer or any other place of their choice, or nearby location of choice etc. (Browne et al., 2001).

The previous studies suggested that when the buying activity becomes a seamless experience it leads to satisfaction and if all the products are possible to get or ordered from one site or shop it gives consumer a strong reason to prefer that site or shop (Bailay, 2003). The marketers can experiment both with sales and cross sales with such buyers. All the shopping motivations act on the psychological i.e., hedonic, and

rational i.e., utilitarian dimensions (Patel and Sharma, 2009) and it is subject to the perceived importance assigned to such motivations by the buyers.

There are nine such motivations studied in the specific Indian context, those studies address the dimension of economic, enjoyment, gratification, idea shopping etc., affecting as motivations to the Indian customers to conduct the act of shopping from the physical setup of the shopping malls. Shopping preference at a certain shop is found motivated the individual if the values expected are justified with the money spent (Devgan and Kaur, 2010), besides the individual's perception about a shop's socioeconomic contribution in the overall growth of the city makes them to prefer certain malls or shops to prefer for shopping (Tiwari and Abraham, 2010). Rational parameters exhibiting the performance of the malls and best practices followed as dimensions of good management and elements of productivity practiced by these malls attract the consumers to explore the malls (Banerjee, 2012) for shopping purposes.

Almost all the available literature addresses the 'home-delivery' as merely a logistical solution to the issue of logistics and have studied it from an administrative perspective such as its effects on logistical efficiency, effects on company profits, individuality and reduction in car traffic and efficient use of transport means as parameters of public advantage. Despite the perceptual importance assigned by the customer, or the buyer is largely ignored (Visser et al., 2014; Van Duin et al., 2016; Cairns, 1996).

The influence of home delivery had been studied in its contextual importance with respect to the areas of product categories and the consumer characteristics. The facility of home delivery if changeable had been found significantly impacting the consumer's purchase decisions regarding the order incidence and order size (Lewis, 2006; Lewis et al., 2006). The operational efficiency of the home delivery had been studied by analyzing its timeliness, by comparing fast and normal delivery time (Collier and Bienstock, 2006; Xing et al. 2010; Rao et al. 2011a; Koufteros et al. 2014; Blut 2016). The influence of home delivery according to various categories of products were studied with content to products such as toys, wine, and jewelry since, consumers tend to buy these products on impulse and want to possess them quickly (Xu et al., 2017).

Many previous studies applied mental accounting as a method of getting the importance assigned by the consumers to the facility of home delivery assuming that the assessment for preference is based on a logical and comparative assessment since home delivery impacts the buying decision in a financial nature (Kahneman and Tversky 1984; Thaler 1985, 1999; Shefrin and Thaler 1988). This approach of mental accounting was extended to examine the consumer feelings with respect to the magnitude of saving possible by availing the home delivery option in the monetary form of a "emotional account", influencing the consumers savings (Levav and McGraw 2009).

Shopping attitude is an evaluative reaction towards a stimulus influenced by demographic characters and type of product, quantity of purchase, frequency of purchase and mode of payment (Hansan, B, 2010; Richard, M, O et al., 2010). This paper adopted these variables as independent variables and intension of shopping has been adopted as dependent variable. All independent variables were categorical with more than three layers. Mode of payment has only two layers, such as cash & digital mode of payment. Shopping intension has been defined as a likelihood subjective character of an individual and is subjected to nature influenced by the attitude of an individual.

An individual's attitude is studied as a function of five specific shopping related elements as shown in the conceptual framework of research model specifically designed for this study.

Research Model:**Figure 1. Study Variables**

(Source: hypothetical model, based on literature review)

Attitude of shopping had been adopted in the study as the independent variable and online buying intension had been adopted as the dependent variable as described in Fig. No.1. The relationship between Shopping attitude (X) and Intension about online buying (Y) in proposed research model is causal. The relationships between the independent, the mediator and the dependent variables had been depicted in form of a path diagram/model. Two of the home delivery formats, i.e., free (without any extra charges) and paid with some monetary charges, had been incorporated as a moderating variable in the proposed model. Availability of internet is the basic pre-requisite for conducting the online buying. But it is not the only motivator hence, additional stimuli had been offered by the e-tellers in the form of home delivery as a free add-on. This model would like to study the moderation effect of one form of home delivery in the relationship of availability of internet and preference for online buying.

Research Methodology:

The relevant data points were collected through a structured questionnaire, which was divided into three sections, the first section was pertaining to the information related to demographic characteristics of the respondents. The demographic characteristics were collected about five individual specific indicators these were respondent's gender, age, educational level, income level and size of family.

The second section had been designed with specific statements indicating their perception about the facility offered by the shops in the form of facility of home delivery of the goods as paid or free and its influence towards selection of shopping site (in case of virtual transaction) or mall (in case of physical transaction).

These statements were framed based on previously tested relevant research papers (Michelle A. et al., 2000) which can measure the selection of shopping malls or sites by the consumers. In all, there were six such statements which were framed to measure the reasons for availing the home delivery either as free add-on or a paid form of service. The respondents were asked to rate these six statements each as their preference on a five-point scale. The respondents were asked to rate separately for paid and for the service when offered as free i.e., the home delivery. The scale used where '1' means 'strongly disagree' and '5' means 'strongly agree'.

The third section was designed to get the shopping habits and frequency of the shopping practices of the customers. Three main questions were designed to the products preferred when there is a free home delivery. If there is any preference in the quantity purchased as an effect of home delivery, it is measured as equivalence of a week, a month, or a bi-monthly equivalence. Do this buying is preferred by personal visiting the shop or it's conducted in the virtual mode. Shopping frequency is measured in three categories such as, once a week, once a month or any time. Lastly, we asked the preferred mode of payment, to measure if any correlation exists between mode of payment and preference for home delivery.

To ensure the content validity, these statements were approved by the subject area experts having specific domain knowledge of retail activities adopted in marketing and only after their consent the questionnaire was administered. The data were collected between December 2024 and February 2025. A team of experienced students with marketing research background and adequate training in qualitative research methods were ensured for the proper data collection. While designing the questionnaire it is deliberately assessed that the respondent should not take more than ten minutes to complete the response in total.

The data collection took place at the home of the participants. Full informed consent was taken from each respondent prior to the acceptance. A total of 300 responses were participated to whom the researcher contacted some of them personally during the pilot study. So, to explain the motive of this study. These respondents were requested to share their views about the home delivery as a type of offer. Random sampling method was applied, and the data were gathered from individuals residing at various residential housing societies located at Mumbai, Navi Mumbai, Thane and Panvel, as it covers the area of Mumbai Metropolitan Regional Development Authority i.e., the MMRDA. It represents the 10th largest populated city of the world (citymeyors.com, Report, 2018).

Research Tool:

Statements measuring the influence of home delivery on the customers' behavior in purchasing products (n = 207)

I always look for the free home delivery facility, because.

1. I find the home deliver facility for convenience
2. I find the home deliver facility for monetary savings
3. I prefer home deliver facility since I don't have my private transportation
4. With home delivery I can buy from a shop located on distance
5. I can use my time for other important activities
6. I want to avoid travelling for taking items from the shop

I don't mind paying for the home delivery facility, because.

1. I find the home delivery facility charges reasonable
2. I find the home delivery facility saves my time
3. I don't have private transportation
4. I can buy from a shop located far from a shop
5. I can monetize my time for other important activities
6. I am not comfortable travelling for taking items from the shop

Sample:

A specific sampling method e.g., convenient non-probability sampling has been adopted in this study to acquire the necessary data by the respondents in Mumbai city since, more than 11.7 million individuals are using the internet and almost all have explored the e-commerce for one or the other occasion (IAMAI, Kantar Report,2020) in India. The convenient sampling has specific advantages such as it is easy to administer and is cost-effective and it gets higher response rate (Eze, Manyeki, Yaw, & Har, 2011; Ritchie, Lewis, Nicholls, McNaughton, & Ormiston, 2014). The questionnaire had been administered on 300 respondents belong to different age-group, both male and female with varied experience in online shopping by conducting a personal interview, and 240 participated and answered the survey. It resulted in 80% response rate. However, after data cleaning only 207 responses were found useful for further analysis as useful and valid. Cleaned and accumulated data were analyzed through Microsoft Excel, and subsequently by analyzing it by using the SPSS process macro version 20.

Sample details: Table No.1Details of sample characteristics

Characteristics	Unit	N	Percentage
Type of preference for home delivery mode	Free	67	32.40%
	Paid	140	67.60%
Gender	Male	70	33.80%
	Female	137	66.20%
Age	Up to 20 Years	28	13.50%
	21 to 30 Years	40	19.30%
	31 to 40 Years	52	25.10%
	41+	87	42.00%
Family Size	2 Persons	27	13.00%
	Up to 5	85	41.10%
	6 and more	95	45.90%
Educational Level	Below Schooling	68	32.90%
	Graduation	75	36.20%
	Post-Graduation	64	30.90%
Product Preferred	Grocery	15	7.20%
	Cosmetics	93	44.90%
	Medicines	31	15.00%
	Home-Decor	68	32.90%
Equivalent-Purchases	A Week Equivalent	26	12.60%
	A Month Equivalent	86	41.50%
	A bi-month Equivalent	95	45.90%
Occasion-of-Shopping	once a week	23	11.10%
	once a month	89	43.00%
	any time	95	45.90%
Payment-Mode	Card	107	51.70%
	Cash	100	48.30%
Total		207	100.00%

(Source: Primary data)

Data Analysis:

The proposed moderation effect had been tested by using a special add on macro called “PROCESS” developed by Andrew F. Hayes. Before the analysis was conducted all the assumptions of measurements being in continuous scale characteristics such as normality, independence, and linearity were tested and detailed analysis conducted only when the data found adhering to all those assumptions.

The causal effect of predictor variable on the outcome variable had been tested by regression-based moderation analysis following the causal step approach. The moderation is due to the offer about the Home-delivery as a free add-on facility, offered by the sellers. These analyses had been used the PROCESS macro for SPSS (Hayes, 2013).

A due precaution was taken to ensure the adherence to the pre-requisite data conditions, i.e., essential e.g., linearity, homoscedasticity, normality of estimation error and independence of observations those parameters were tested and once they were found as proper, the researcher tested the prescribed moderation models were tested for mode of shopping which was measured by two level categorical (online/ physical) dependent variable(Y) for payment modes two level categorical (cash/by card) (X) and home-delivery of the products when its offered as free service “M1” were studied in the model, and the consumer details were incorporated as covariates these were eight parameters e.g., 5 demographical characteristics, such as gender, age, family size, education level, income-level with 3 shopping related parameters such as, product preferred, equivalent buying, occasion of purchase, with these parameters a model has been designed and the moderation effects were tested, for the sample size of 207.

The mediation effect of free home delivery:

The key features of the test results were as described below, for free home delivery the designed model tested the moderation of free home delivery found significant, as described in the model summary Table No.1.

Table No.1 Model details with free home delivery

R	R-Sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
0.5854	0.3437	0.1753	11.411	9.000	197.00	0.000

(Source: primary data analysis)

The designed model can explain mediation impact up to 34.37% accurately with the independent variables.

Model-free home delivery	coefficient	standard Error	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	2.5632	0.3166	8.0963	0.0000	1.9389	3.1876
payment mode	-0.1762	0.0509	-3.4652	0.0007	-0.2765	-0.0759
gender	0.1144	0.0716	1.5985	0.1115	-0.0267	0.2555
age	0.0957	0.0315	3.0336	0.0027	0.0335	0.1579
family-size	0.059	0.4308	0.1371	0.8911	-0.7905	0.9085
education	0.0726	0.0432	1.6803	0.0945	-0.0126	0.1577
Product type	-0.0006	0.0339	-0.0169	0.9866	-0.0673	0.0662
equivalent	0.0207	0.4338	0.0477	0.962	-0.8349	0.8762
occasion	0.2744	0.0499	5.5042	0.0000	0.1761	0.3727
income-level	0.0042	0.0316	0.134	0.8936	-0.0582	0.0667

(Source: primary data analysis)

Two shopping preference characteristics incorporated as test variables in the model e.g., payment mode used (cash, card), buying occasion (ones in a week, ones in a month and any time) and age of the buyers (up to 20 years, 21 to 30, 31-40 and 41+), were tested significant, for these items both LLCI and ULCI values $\neq 0$ indicates a significant moderated effect between IV and MV. The “t” value for payment mode and product type was negative it showed the non-homogeneity of the classification represented by the sample tested in the model.

Since the payment mode had been measured in categorical manner the negative coefficient value indicated that the modification effect of free home delivery reduces for card-based payments. While as free home delivery found attractive for those who prefer to buy on cash. The negative coefficient value for product had established that free home delivery influences on the grocery category of products, while as its impact reduced for the home décor products item category.

The moderation effect of paid home delivery:

The key features of the test results were as described below, for paid home delivery the designed model tested the mediation of paid home delivery found significant, as described in the model summary Table No.2.

Table No.2 Model details with paid home delivery

R	R-Sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
0.6414	0.4114	0.1095	15.3003	9	197	0.00

(Source: primary data analysis)

The designed model can explain mediation impact up to 41.14% accurately with the independent variables.

Model-free home delivery	coefficient	standard Error	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	2.8045	0.2502	11.2077	0.00	2.311	3.298
payment mode	0.0249	0.0402	0.6188	0.5368	-0.0544	0.1041
gender	-0.1174	0.0566	-2.0755	0.0392	-0.229	-0.0058
age	-0.022	0.0249	-0.8828	0.3784	-0.0712	0.0272
family-size	1.1129	0.3405	3.2688	0.0013	0.4415	1.7844
education	0.0296	0.0341	0.8657	0.3877	-0.0378	0.0969
Product type	-0.0728	0.0268	-2.7218	0.0071	-0.1256	-0.0201
equivalent	-1.0417	0.3429	-3.0379	0.0027	-1.7179	-0.3655
occasion	0.2617	0.0394	6.641	0.000	0.184	0.3394
income-level	0.1232	0.025	4.9239	0.000	0.0738	0.1725

(Source: primary data analysis)

Six shopping characteristics incorporated as test variables in the model e.g., gender (male, female), family size of buyers measured in three categories (2 Nos, up to 5 Nos. and 6+ Nos.), product type (grocery, cosmetics, medicines, and home décor), equivalent purchase (a week equivalent, a month equivalent and bi-month equivalent), buying occasion (ones in a week, ones in a month and any time) and income level (below Rs. 15,000, Rs. 15,001 to Rs. 25,000 and Rs. 25,001+) tested significant, for these items both LLCI (Lower Limit Confidence Interval) and ULCI (Upper Limit Confidence Interval) values $\neq 0$ indicate a significant moderate effect between IV and MV. The “t” values for gender, age, product type and equivalent purchase was negative it showed the non-homogeneity of the classification represented by the sample tested in the model.

Since the gender had been measured in categorical manner the negative coefficient value indicated that the modification effect of paid home delivery reduces for female buyers. While as paid home delivery found attractive for males. The negative coefficient value for product had established that home delivery offered in paid format influences the grocery category of products, while its impact reduced for the home décor products category. The negative coefficient value for equivalent purchase had established that paid home delivery influences purchases in high frequency i.e., items preferred to be purchased on a weekly basis while as items which were preferred to be purchased ones in a two-month duration paid home delivery was less impactful.

The direct, indirect, and total effect of moderation:

The results of the direct effect between the payment mode and mode of shopping had been estimated at -0.4556 as showed in the Table No. 3. the true indirect effect had been recorded between -1.0439 and 0.1127 with 95% confidence. Since zero is in the 95% confidence interval, it was concluded that the direct effect indeed significantly indifferent from zero at $p > 0.05$ (two tailed).

Table No.3 Details of direct effect of X on Y

Effect	se	Z	p	LLCI	ULCI
-0.4656	0.2951	-1.5779	0.1146	-1.0439	0.1127

(Source: primary data analysis)

The results of the indirect effects of the two moderating variables tested separately by applying the bootstrapped estimate for confirmation, since the non-parametric method for each of the parameter had been examined by the bootstrapped confidence interval, as shown in Table No.4. Since the confidence intervals contained zero hence, the true effect size was indifferent from ‘the direct effect’, in other words, there was no mediation by those items in the model under testing. The mediation tested for the two parameters stands correct.

Table No.4 Details of indirect effect of X on Y

	Effect	Boot SE	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
TOTAL	0.1514	0.1105	-0.035	0.4011
Free-home delivery	0.1195	0.0953	-0.0335	0.3424
Paid-home delivery	0.0319	0.0607	-0.0816	0.1645

(Source: primary data analysis)

Path diagram with results:

(Source: primary data analysis)

Discussion:

In the competitive environment of business, the online business domain needs to examine the effectiveness of the non-monetary elements experimented, such as free home delivery. The present paper tried to measure the moderation effect in a scientific method to estimate the mediation effect of home delivery on Intension of shopping measured as mode of shopping when various payment modes are possible to explore. The point estimate of the paid home delivery option was tested positive while as the mediation effect of free home delivery was estimated negative. But the direct effect between the payment mode and mode of shopping was negative.

The point estimate between payment mode and the mode of shopping is modified by the paid home deliveries. In this testing the researcher tested eight individual characteristics to improve the practical application of model by the practitioners.

The individual characteristics of the sample tested has established that the heterogeneity of the consumer profile had an equal determination in defining the overall mediation effect of any promotional facility that provided with binary options.

Findings:

Free home delivery even though presented by the marketers with a bias that it may have more moderation effect of both frequency and magnitude of shopping the testing model revealed that paid home delivery had a certain moderation effect based on gender, family size, type of product, how much the buyer preferred to buy in one go of shopping, occasion of buying and income level. The values of the point estimates estimated by applying bootstrapping and without bootstrapping remained the same, hence the moderation impact of home delivery needs to be gauged on a big size sample for commercial purposes.

References:

1. Bailay, R. 2003, In India, shopping takes on a whole new meaning. The Wall Street Journal, December 16, New York. Retrieved 18 August 2016, from https://businessperspectives.org/media/zoo/applications/publishing/templates/article/assets/js/pdfjs/web/viewer.php?file=/pdfproxy.php?item_id:4625
2. Blut, M. 2016, "E-Service Quality: Development of a Hierarchical Model." *Journal of Retailing* 92(4):500–17
3. Boyer, K.K.; Frohlich, M.T.; Hult, T.G. 2005, *Extending the Supply Chain: How Cutting-Edge Companies Bridge the Critical Last Mile into Customers' Homes*. American Management Association, USA. 252 p.
4. Browne, M.; Allen, J.; Anderson, S; Jackson, M. 2001, *Overview of home deliveries in the UK*. University of Westminster and Freight Transport Association (FTA), a study for the DTI.
5. Cairns, S. 1996, *Delivering alternatives*, *Transport Policy* 3(4): 155–176.
6. Collier, J.E., and Bienstock, C.C. 2006, "Measuring Service Quality in E-Retailing." *Journal of Service Research* 8 (3):260–75
7. Gould, J. 1998, *Driven to Shop? Role of Transportation in Future Home Shopping*, *Transportation Research Record* 1617: 149–156.
8. Hasan, B., 2010, *Exploring gender differences in online shopping attitude*, *Computers in human behaviour*", Vol.26, pp.597-601.

9. Hays, T.; Keskinocak, P.; De López, V. M. 2005, Strategies and challenges of internet grocery retailing logistics. In Genus, J. (Ed.), Applications of Supply Chain Management and E-Commerce Research, Springer, 217-252.
10. Hobbs, J. E. 2020, Food supply chains during the COVID-19 pandemic, Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics 68: 171-176.
11. Kahneman, D., and Tversky, A. 1984, "Choices, Values, and Frames." American Psychologist 39(4):341–50
12. Kämäräinen, V.; Punakivi, M. 2002, Developing Cost-effective Operations for the e-Grocery Supply Chain, International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications 5(3): 285–298.
13. Koufteros, X., Droge, C., Heim, G., Massad, N., and Vickery, S.K. 2014, "Encounter Satisfaction in E-Tailing: Are the Relationships of Order Fulfillment Service Quality with Its Antecedents and Consequences Moderated by Historical Satisfaction?" Decision Sciences 45(1):5–48
14. Kull, T. J.; Boyer, K.; Calantone, R. 2007. Last-mile supply chain efficiency: an analysis of learning curves in online ordering, International Journal of Operations & Production Management 27(4): 409-434.
15. Lewis, M. 2006, "The Effect of Shipping Fees on Customer Acquisition, Customer Retention, and Purchase Quantities." Journal of Retailing 82(1):13–23
16. Lewis, M. 2006, "The Effect of Shipping Fees on Customer Acquisition, Customer Retention, and Purchase Quantities." Journal of Retailing 82(1):13–23
17. Lewis, M., Singh, V., and Fay, S. 2006, "An Empirical Study of the Impact of Nonlinear Shipping and Handling Fees on Purchase Incidence and Expenditure Decisions." Marketing Science 25(1):51–64
18. Lim, S. F. W. T.; Jin, X.; Srai, J. S. 2018, Consumer-driven e-commerce, International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management 48(3): 308–332.
19. Rao, S., Griffis, S.E., and Goldsby, T.J. 2011, "Failure to Deliver? Linking Online Order Fulfillment Glitches with Future Purchase Behavior." Journal of Operations Management 29(7–8):692–703
20. Richard, M., O., Chebat, J. C., Yang, Z.Y., & Putrevu, S., 2010, " A Proposed Model of online Consumer Behaviour: Assessing the role of gender", Journal of Business Research, Vol.63, PP.926-934.
21. Shefrin, H.M., and Thaler, R.H. 1988, "The Behavioral LifeCycle Hypothesis." Economic Inquiry 26(4):609–43
22. State of India's Digital Economy, 2023, Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations (ICRIER).
23. Thaler, R.H. 1999, "Mental Accounting Matters." Journal of Behavioral Decision Making 12(3):183–206
24. Van Duin, J. H. R.; De Goffau, W.; Wiegmans, B.; Tavasszy, L. A.; Saes, M. 2016, Improving Home Delivery Efficiency by Using Principles of Address Intelligence for B2C Deliveries, Transportation Research Procedia 12: 14-25.
25. Visser, J.; Nemoto, T.; Browne, M. 2014, Home Delivery, and the Impacts on Urban Freight Transport: A Review, Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 125: 15–27.
26. Xing, Y., Grant, D.B., McKinnon, A.C., and Fernie, J. 2010, "Physical Distribution Service Quality in Online Retailing." International Journal of Physical Distribution and Logistics Management 40(5):415–32

27. Xu, X., Munson, C.L., and Zeng, S. 2017, "The Impact of E-Service Offerings on the Demand of Online Customers." *International Journal of Production Economics* 184:231–44
28. Michelle A. Morganosky, Brenda J. Cude. 2000, "Consumer response to online grocery shopping", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 28 Iss 1 pp. 17 – 26
29. Eze, U. C., L. H. Yaw J. K. Manyeki and L. C. Har. 2011, 'Factors Affecting Internet Banking Adoption among Young Adults: Evidence from Malaysia', *International Conference on Social Science and Humanity, IPEDR*, 5.
30. Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., Nicholls, C., McNaughton, J., and Ormiston, R. (2014). *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers*. SAGE Publications.
31. The Indian Telecom Services Performance Indicators January – March 2021, Telecom Regulatory Authority of India, 2021.
32. IAMAI, Kantar Report, Internet Adoption in India, 2020.